

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BBF TECHNOLOGY ADOPTER AND NON-BBF TECHNOLOGY ADOPTER ON SOYBEAN CROP IN PARBHANI DISTRICT OF MARATHWADA REGION, (M.S)Rani J. Khandagale^{1*}, Sachin S. More², Tukaram B. Munde³^{1*} M.Sc. student, ² Associate Professor and ³ Associate Professor,

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Abstract

The Broad bed and furrow system has been mainly developed at the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-arid Tropics (ICRISAT) in India. A comprehensive research programme was carried out on-station for eight years before being taken for on-farm adaptive research at Tadthanaple in Medak district. BBF system resulted in 35 percent yield increase in soybean during rainy season. Soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) is globally cultivated leading oilseed crop known as golden bean for its various nutritional qualities. The major soybean producing countries are Brazil, Canada, China, India and USA. The crop was introduced in India in 1000 AD. Globally India stands in fourth position with the cultivable area of 11.40 m ha and fifth with a production capacity of 13.78 MT (FAO STAT, 2020). Area under soybean counted was [46.01 lakh ha in Maharashtra. Maximum area under soybean was recorded in Latur division i.e. 17.51 lakh ha. Because of its lucrative nature and numerous benefits, the crop is the first and foremost option of millions of small and marginal farmers, and it plays an important role in the farming community's socio-economic transformation. The crop is primarily grown under rainfed conditions, and rainfall distribution has a significant impact on yield.

Keywords: BBF Technology, Soybean yield, Occupation, farm size, education, Family income.

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) is globally cultivated leading oilseed crop known as golden bean for its various nutritional qualities. The major soybean producing countries are Brazil, Canada, China, India and USA. The crop was introduced in India in 1000 AD. Area under soybean counted was 46.01 lakh ha in Maharashtra. Maximum area under soybean was recorded in Latur division i.e. 17.51 lakh ha. Because of its lucrative nature and numerous benefits, the crop is the first and foremost option of millions of small and marginal farmers, and it plays an important role in the farming community's socio-economic transformation.

Many benefits of soybean such as its use for human nutrition have been widely explored in Asian countries including India. Focus of the study was to observed utilization of BBF Technology on soybean crop recommended by VNMKV. Socio-economic characters of BBF technology adopter and non-adopter was important factors. Such as age, education, farm size, Family size, Occupation, Land holding, Cropping Pattern, Annual income etc.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Parbhani district of Maharashtra state in year 2022-23. Parbhani district is one of the leading BBF Technology on Soybean of Maharashtra. Out of 9 talukas of Parbhani district, purposively selected 2 talukas viz. Parbhani and Jintur. Three villages

were selected randomly from each taluka. And, total 6 villages were selected for the study. A random sampling procedure was followed for the selection of the twenty BBF Technology adopters and non-adopters from each village. Thus, 60 BBF Technology adopter and 60 non-adopters were selected for the study. The data was collected with the help of well structured, pre-tested schedule through personal contact. In analytical technique, study of socio-economic characteristics of BBF Technology adopter and non-adopters will be analyzed with help of descriptive statistics i.e., mean, frequency and percentage.

Results and discussions

An objective is undertaken for study to know the socio-economic profile of BBF Technology adopter and non-adopters an insight in the table 1.1. Shows that the average age of the BBF technology adopters 45.15 and non-adopters 50.13, which is between 39-59 years, mostly regarded as the active productive age, meaning that the population is active. This middle-aged group people also having great sense of responsibility, enough energy and hardworking than older and too young aged BBF technology adopters and non-adopters in the study area. The finding about age are concurs with those of Reddy and Sen (2014) and Kumar *et.al.* (2019). It was revealed from the table that the number of nucleous families were found low in case of adopters 71.66 percent and more in non-adopters 90 percent.

Table 1.1: Socio economic characters of BBF Technology adopters and non-adopters.

Sr.No.	Particulars	Adopter		Non-adopter	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender				
a)	Male	55	91.67	53	88.33
b)	Female	5	8.33	7	11.67
	Total	60	100.00	60	100.00
2	Average Age(year)	45.15		50.13	
3	Farming Experience	23.67		24	
4	Education				
a)	Illiterate	0	0.00	3	5.00
b)	Primary	5	8.33	14	23.33
c)	Secondary	10	16.66	20	33.33
d)	HSC	17	28.33	16	26.67
e)	Graduate	21	35	5	8.33
f)	Above Graduate	7	11.66	2	3.33
	Total	60	100.00	60	100.00
5	Occupation				
a)	Agriculture	44	73.33	53	88.33
b)	Service	7	11.67	2	3.33
c)	Business	9	15.00	5	8.33

	Total	60	100.00	60	100.00
6	Family type				
a)	Joint	17	28.33	6	10.00
b)	Nucleous	43	71.66	54	90.00
	Total	60	100.00	60	100.00
7	Farm size				
a)	Marginal	1	1.67	11	18.33
b)	Small	3	5.00	42	70
c)	Semi Medium	35	58.33	4	6.66
d)	Medium	19	31.67	2	3.33
e)	Large	2	3.33	1	1.66
	Total	60	100.00	60	100.00
8	Family income	497740.3		244816.7	
9	Social Participation	0.96	100.00	0.31	100.00
10	Livestock				
a)	Bullock Pair	26	21.85	18	50.00
b)	Cow	32	26.89	6	16.67
c)	Buffalo	30	25.21	4	11.11
d)	Goat	31	26.05	8	22.22
e)	Other	0	0.00	0	0.00
	Total	119	100.00	36	100.00

The results also revealed that social participation is optimum adopters 0.96 and non-adopters with 0.31. It is observed that social participation has great impact on adoption of BBF Technology. The analyses of occupational pattern revealed that agriculture was main occupation of farmers with 73.33 per cent adopters and 88.33 percent non-adopters, followed by service 11.67 percent adopters and 3.33 non-adopters and business 15 percent adopters and 8.33 percent non-adopters.

The study of farm size revealed that most of the high adopters were found with semi-medium was 58.33 percent, medium 31.67 percent adopters and 3.33 non-adopters, small 70.00 percent Non-adopters and 5.00 percent adopters and marginal 18.33 percent non-adopters. Semi-medium farmers were found least in per cent in adoption of BBF technology. Family income of high adopters was Rs.497740.3 and low non-adopters was Rs.244816.7.

Conclusion

Profile of adopters and non-adopters was more or less similar in respect of age, it was clear from the result that most of the respondent were middle aged. While profile of growers and non-adopters varied in respect of their land holding, annual income, social participation and land holding. Majority of BBF Technology adopter and non-BBF Technology adopter having nucleous families, regarding to family income it was reported that high adopters and low non-adopters. Optimization of social participation adopters and minimized non-adopters hence they are far away from information regarding new Technology. Agriculture was reported as major occupation in the study area followed by service and very low adopters and non-adopters are engaged in business. Large number of semi-medium farmers were reported in study area followed by marginal, small, medium. Family size of all adopters and non-adopters was different. It can be suggested from the study that non-adopters need to adopt

recommended technology in order to improve livelihood and family income.

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